

Three Self Patriotic Movement (TSPM)

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** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

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The Three Self Patriotic Movement (TSPM) is a politically oriented "patriotic religious association" that was established in the early 1950s by a group of diverse but prominent Protestants. The movement's name stems from its core principles of "self-governance, self-support, and self-propagation." Strictly speaking, the movement is not a church, but rather a collection of Protestant churches that are affiliated with the movement and who register with the state through the TSPM. The organization aims to represent Protestant believers in China and engage with the Chinese state on their behalf. To that end, TSPM maintains committees at not only the national level, but also the provincial, municipal, and county/district levels. The TSPM works in partnership with the China Christian Council, whose remit is to deal with doctrinal and pastoral issues, and, together, they are referred to as the "Two Committees" (lianghui 两会). This entry understands the TSPM through the lens of several, TSPM-affiliated churches in the city of Huanghaicheng, a pseudonym for a city of approximately 2 million people on China's eastern seaboard. The research informing this entry is Mark McLeister's extensive ethnographic work in Huanghaicheng, which has been continuing since 2009. Because of this detailed focus, there may be slight variations between the answers to the questions presented here and other TSPM-affiliated churches in different parts of China. TSPM-affiliated churches are distinguished by their belief in a threefold yet single God (made up of God, Jesus, and the Holy Spirit), who is omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent, who created the world, and who is purely good. As well, members of TSPM-affiliated churches believe in an immortal soul that can be rewarded in Heaven or punished in Hell after death and that Jesus Christ is the messiah who will return at the end of the world to save the faithful and create a "New Heaven and New Earth" (xintianxindi 新天新地). TSPM-affiliated churches understand the universe in terms of a three-fold division between that which is "of God" shuling 属灵 (and Jesus and the Holy Spirit), that which is related to Satan (sadan mogui 撒旦魔鬼) and "evil spirits" (xieling 邪灵), and that which is "of the flesh" (shu ruoti 属肉体) or "of the world" (shushi 属世). Individual sins and sinful acts lead to a kind of break or opening (pokou 破口) in one's spiritual life that can allow evil spirits to influence and even dominate one's life. Evil spirits are also thought to be capable of possessing individuals or "playing tricks" (kaiwanxiao 开玩笑) on them such as by preventing keys from working in locks or hiding one's keys. Previous scholarship has tended to present TSPM churches as staid and austere, befitting the organization's image as a modern religion, while discussing "household churches" as forms of "popular Christianity" that deal with more sensorially and aesthetically rich forms of religious experience in a way that echoes other popular religious practices in China. However, detailed ethnographic work demonstrates that these two religious modalities are present within TSPM, with the more formal aspect featured in weekly Sunday sermons and the latter aspect more prominent in small prayer meetings among church adherents throughout the week. The latter aspect is defined in terms of ling'en 灵恩. Composed of the characters meaning "spirit" and "grace," this term is the same as that used in "charismatic" or "Pentecostal" movements. However, its adherents understand it as referring to distinct forms of practices unaffiliated with those movements. In brief, ling'en refers to being filled with (or moved by) the Holy Spirit as a result of prayer. It is defined in sensorial and aesthetic terms and is associated with feelings of joy and peace that can easily move a person to tears. The gifts given by the Holy Spirit can also include the ability to exorcize demons, heal the sick, utter prophetic words, and speak in tongues. Although

not possessed uniformly by church leaders, ling'en qualities are an important measure of authority within TSPM-affiliated congregations. The atmosphere of the prayer meetings that are the frequent site of ling'en experiences form a strong contrast to the staid atmosphere of Sunday worship services and may be considered a more personal and sensorially rich form of worship than the "public face" of TSPM-affiliated churches presented in Sunday services. Nevertheless, participants emphasize that such prayer meetings are "warm" rather than "hot" (renao 热闹), as the term renao is thought to be associated with activities that are "of the world" rather than "of God," and, in some cases, even with evil spirits. Protestantism is one of China's fastest growing religious movements and the complex array of interactions between the leaders and participants of TSPM-affiliated churches and the state has many potential implications in Chinese society, especially in relation to issues of state-religion interaction, as well as the role of the law in state actions.

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2021 CE

Region: People's Republic of China

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

Borders of present-day China

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

Notes: Christianity is one of the "official" religions of China and exist alongside a variety of religious traditions, such as Islam, Buddhism, and Daoism (McLeister 2013, 237 no.12).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: Members of TSPM-affiliated churches consider Protestantism to be the one true faith and regard other religions as "evil" and the work of the devil, Satan (sadan mogui 撒旦魔鬼) or "evil spirits" (xieling 邪灵). Consequently, church followers actively proselytize to convince non-members to convert to Protestantism and reject other religious traditions (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— No

Notes: Although it is possible that TSPM-affiliated church practices, particularly those related to "signs and wonders," may be influenced by other religious movements (such as Chinese popular religion), these influences are not consciously pursued by TSPM-affiliated churches as Protestantism is considered the one true religion (McLeister 2019, 138).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Cultural contact between TSPM-affiliated churches and other religious groups may be neutral as church members may consciously avoid coming into contact with other religious groups and focusing exclusively on their own religious community. The reason for this is the possibility that other religious sites may constitute an inherent danger to a church member's spiritual life (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Although a person may be a member of a TSPM-affiliated church practically from birth

(due to the commitment of their parents), membership in the church is not automatic and all children must undergo baptism in order to become a church member.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: One can choose to convert to Protestantism, in which case one must be baptized.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Protestant groups, TSPM-affiliated churches require that members be baptized.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: TSPM-affiliated churches actively engage in proselytizing based on the belief that Protestantism is the one true faith. This practice is mandated for religious professionals such as pastors and is strongly encouraged, though not required for lay believers. While pastors may proselytize through overseas missions or church services, it is not uncommon for lay believers to pass out leaflets in public places encouraging passersby to convert and join their church. In rare cases, pastors may join in this activity and even lead lay believers in singing church songs to attract passersby and make it easier to hand out leaflets (McLeister 2021, 252-253). While this type of direct involvement by religious professionals is rare, religious leadership at multiple levels of the Two Committees supports it by encouraging leafletting in sermons and by printing leaflets for churches as well as providing the finances needed for printing them (McLeister 2021, 246). Passing out leaflets in public spaces is technically prohibited by state authorities, but ambiguities in the law, inconsistencies in its application, and the personal relationships between local state officials and religious professionals mean that this practice generally continues (McLeister 2021). In addition to local practices like leafletting, some TSPM-affiliated churches also engage in programs such as "Back to Jerusalem," "a mission-oriented project to complete world evangelisation" (McLeister 2013, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: One of the Three Self Patriotic Movement's main purposes is to interface with the government on behalf of those churches registered with it. As such, the TSPM acts as an "official" religious organization and works with government branches such as the Religious Affairs Bureau (RAB) (zongjiaoju 宗教局) or Section (zongjiaoke 宗教课) and the various churches affiliated with the TSPM are also registered with the RAB through the TSPM (McLeister 2013, 236; 2019, 128). By registering with the state through the TSPM, a given church becomes a "venue for religious activities" (zongjiao huodong changsuo 宗教活动场所), meaning that it is protected under China's religious policy. At the same time, this also provides the state with a means to monitor and police church activities as achieving this status means that a church is allowed to conduct "legitimate" religious activities only (McLeister 2019, 128). At the local level, individual church leaders work within this institutional framework with local RAB officials. The relationships between these figures are the local means by which TSPM-affiliated churches draw support from, and negotiate with, the state, as well as the local means by which the state monitors and regulates church activities (McLeister 2013). At times, these relationships provide a way for local churches to pursue activities, such as leafletting, that are not strictly allowed under China's religious policy (McLeister 2021). Recently, the specifics of this situation has changed slightly as the State Administration for Religious Affairs was absorbed into the United Front Work Department in 2018. This means that now church leaders deal directly with United Front Work Department officials, although some of these officials were formerly Religious Affairs Bureau officials.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: TSPM-affiliated churches are permitted to run on a tax-free basis.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: However, leaders have lost their standing for violating church rules, such as divorcing their spouses.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although exact numbers are impossible to come by, it is notable that Christianity in general is one of China's fastest growing religions (McLeister 2019, 132).

Specific to this answer:

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although exact numbers are impossible to come by, it is notable that Christianity in general is one of China's fastest growing religions (McLeister 2019, 132).

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: "Small" here is intended in a relative sense as the TSPM is a large organization, including many different affiliated churches. However, it is still only a part of China's total Christian community and, at a global level, the international Protestant and Christian communities.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The principal leadership role within the TSPM is that of pastor. Pastors are religious specialists trained through seminaries who act as the leaders of local churches as well as the members of the regional and national committees of the TSPM that oversee affiliated churches within their designated areas of authority. In addition to pastors, other leadership positions include "elder" (zhanglao 长老) and "preacher" (chuandaoren 传道人) (McLeister 2019, 129-130). Officially, leadership positions in seminaries and the TSPM committees are appointed by the local state. Applications are handled by the lianghui and suitable candidates are suggested by the lianghui to the state. Whether or not a candidate is chosen for a given position is dependent on how they are regarded in the Protestant community and, as described elsewhere in this entry, ling'en functions as a key factor in how a given candidate is regarded (McLeister 2019, 144). At the level of individual churches, the official leadership hierarchy is often supplemented by lay church members who assist the official leadership with "pastoral care and leading meetings." In certain instances, such as Decheng church in Huanghaicheng, these lay members form a collective leadership body together with the official church leaders (McLeister 2019, 129-130).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: As described above, the leaders of individual churches are overseen by councils at the regional and national levels.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Provincial, municipal, district, and county committees of the TSPM provide oversight for the leadership of individual, TSPM-affiliated churches (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The TSPM maintains a national committee and works together with the China Christian Council (together, the two are referred to as the "Two Committees" lianghui 两会). Below the national level, there are additional committees at the provincial, municipal, district and county levels (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: In addition to the leadership of individual TSPM-affiliated churches, the TSPM maintains committees at the national, provincial, municipal, and often county/district levels (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: It is possible for any person to receive gifts from the Holy Spirit, which can include speaking in tongues (shuo fangyan 说方言), interpreting tongues (fan fangyan 翻方言), special wisdom (zhahui 智慧) and knowledge (zhishi 知识), dreams, prophetic words (yuyande yanyu 预言的言语), exorcising evil spirits (gangui 赶鬼), and the ability to heal people from physical and psychological illnesses (yibing 疫病) (McLeister 2019, 136). More importantly, ling'en qualities are considered important signs to verify that a given leader or leadership candidate is "of God" (shuling 属灵). An example would be that a pastor's preaching is "clear, powerful, inspiring,

knowledgeable, does not draw attention to the speaker, and...leads people to convert" (McLeister 2019, 144). Any and all of these gifts can be taken away and they are not thought to derive from the office or rank of a given leader. As such, we cannot say that leaders are uniformly considered to possess supernatural powers or qualities, only that it is possible, and sometimes necessary, for them to be so considered.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Powers are inherited:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Church leaders are officially selected by the state at all levels of hierarchy and are required to undergo political background checks. However, the lianghui plays a key role in this process by managing applications and recommending those they view as suitable candidates. When considered potential candidates, the lianghui focus on how a given candidate is regarded in the Protestant community, a factor closely related to issues of ling'en as described above (McLeister 2019, 144).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: The views of the congregation play a part in the selection of leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian denominations, TSPM-affiliated church's take the Bible as their primary scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: However, the words of the Bible are considered to have great power, particularly when spoken aloud. This power is enhanced by detailed knowledge of scripture as such knowledge

allows an individual to recite a Bible passage appropriate to the situation in which they find themselves. An example of the power of the Bible's words is the use of scriptural readings in exorcisms (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is considered to be a collection of accounts of literal truth written down by human authors (McLeister 2019, 136). As these authors recorded miraculous events and can include prophets, the Bible can be considered to be "inspired" by God even if the precise words were not literally revealed by God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common

people, general populace)

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Ordained pastors who are trained through seminary schools are the primary institution for transmitting and interpreting the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: A common feature of TSPM-affiliated churches are Bible study sessions, which are sometimes used to learn English as preparation for participation in "Back to Jerusalem," "a mission-oriented project to complete world evangelisation" (McLeister 2013, 239). Churches also offer Sunday school (zhurixue 主日学) to instruct children in church teachings and the Bible (McLeister 2013, 239). Potential conflicts between interpretations by Bible study groups and pastors are ameliorated by the fact that the Bible is typically interpreted literally (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common

people, general populace)

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, pastors are specially trained in seminaries and are the chief transmitters of the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible can be considered a canon unto itself due to its two testaments and multiple books.

Specific to this answer:

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Generally speaking, the centres of TSPM-affiliated religious practice are Protestant churches (tang 堂), some of which are instances of monumental religious architecture. For example, Decheng church in Huanghaicheng is a stone building that was built in 1922 by a group of Chinese Protestants (McLeister 2019, 128). Some Three-Self-affiliated congregations meet in rented buildings or in buildings which have been purchased and converted for church use.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The most salient feature of TSPM-affiliated church iconography is the cross. In many cases, crosses are affixed to the top of church roofs and, in some instances, may even be lit at night to enhance their visibility (McLeister 2019, 128). Other aspects of doctrine may also be present. For example, the main gate of the Desheng church in Huanghaicheng is topped by the words, "God loves the people of the world" (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian churches, TSPM-affiliated churches are often characterized by crosses on their roofs. In some instances, roof-top crosses may be illuminated at night (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Churches are considered sacred sites. See the comments above for a more detailed discussion.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: TSPM-affiliated churches draw a sharp distinction between the immaterial world (referring to both that which is "of God" 属灵 shuling and Satan sadan mogui 撒旦魔鬼 and "evil spirits" xieling 邪灵) and that which is "of the flesh" 属弱体 or "of the world" (shushi 属世). The immortal soul is part of that which belongs to God (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Bodily resurrection

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: TSPM-affiliated Protestant churches believe in a bifurcated afterlife composed of Heaven above (where the good are reward) and Hell below (where the wicked are punished).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, and until recently, many Christians in Huanghaicheng were buried in cemeteries. In line with current state burial policy, most Christians are cremated. It is not uncommon for Christians in Huanghaicheng to have their ashes scattered at sea in a simple family ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Cremation with scattering of ashes

Notes: In line with current state burial policy, most Christians are cremated. It is not uncommon for Christians in Huanghaicheng to have their ashes scattered at sea in a simple family ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: God is the supreme being and creator of the cosmos. He is omniscient, omnipresent, omnipotent, and completely good. God exists in three forms: God, Jesus, and the Holy Spirit (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God is the supreme being and creator of the cosmos. He is omniscient, omnipresent, omnipotent, and completely good. God exists in three forms: God, Jesus, and the Holy Spirit (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Everything

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common

people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Unless "high god" means only God the Father when we would say Jesus Christ and the Holy Spirit. However, all three are considered one (doctrine of the Trinity).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: God is the supreme being and creator of the cosmos. He is omniscient, omnipresent, omnipotent, and completely good. God exists in three forms: God, Jesus, and the Holy Spirit (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Prayer; ling'en

Notes: At least in TSPM-affiliated churches in Huanghaicheng, a crucial aspect of God's communication is the notion of ling'en 灵恩. Composed of characters meaning "spirit" and "grace," ling'en is described as "the Holy Spirit's grace (or

favor)" (shenglingde endian 圣灵的恩典) or as "the Holy Spirit's gift(s)" (shenglingde enci 圣灵的恩赐). It refers to a method of communicating with God and receiving power from God by being "filled with the Spirit" (chongman shenglin 充满圣灵) or being "moved by the spirit" (bei shengling gandong 被圣灵感动). This state cannot be controlled because the Holy Spirit is (all)powerful and recipients often describe such a state in terms of joy, contentment, and peace. Sometimes, such an experience can even cause one to weep (McLeister 2019, 135-136). Among the many gifts that one can receive from the Holy Spirit are: speaking in tongues (shuo fangyan 说方言), interpreting tongues (fan fangyan 翻方言), special wisdom (zhahui 智慧) and knowledge (zhishi 知识), dreams, prophetic words (yuyande yanyu 预言的言语), exorcising evil spirits (gangui 甘鬼), and the ability to heal people from physical and psychological illnesses (yibing 疫病) (McLeister 2019, 136). In addition, there are also leadership "gifts," including the positions of "pastor," "teacher," and "preacher." "Prophet" is considered such a gift as well, but it is acknowledged that there is no longer any need for prophets. As well, traits like "insight" (kanjian 看见) or specific aptitudes for business or learning languages may also be considered gifts from the Holy Spirit. The Bible plays a key role in determining what instances are authentic cases or signs of being filled with the Holy Spirit, but its examples are not considered exhaustive (McLeister 2019, 136-137).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased humans go to either Heaven (if they were faithful and good) or Hell (if they were sinful and wicked). There is little suggestion that they maintain an active involvement with the living.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– No

Notes: Although this is difficult to answer definitively, it is likely "no" due to the understandings of "the new heaven and the new earth" where everything will be "made new."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Residents of Heaven or Hell

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to God (and Jesus and the Holy Spirit), "evil spirits" (xieling 邪灵) and Satan (sadan mogui 撒旦魔鬼) are also present (McLeister 2019, 136). The latter have the ability to possess, harm, and "play tricks" (kaiwanxiao 开玩笑) on mortal humans such as hiding their glasses (McLeister 2019, 130-131; 136). Consequently, humans must be careful to avoid sinful acts as sin creates a break or opening (pokou 破口) through which evil spirits can influence and even dominate one's life (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There are accounts of exorcisms where those involved reported noises, feelings of coldness and furniture in the room shaking when the demon/s was/were "cast out."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally

visible (in public):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Agents of punishment

Notes: Because God is all powerful and benevolent, the acts of evil spirits and Satan may be interpreted as acts of punishment conducted, ultimately, in line with God's will.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The only reference to such beings is from the biblical account in Genesis where the Nephilim are the offspring of humans/angels. It's not clear to what extent they might be considered divine, though.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to God (and Jesus and the Holy Spirit), "evil spirits" (xieling 邪灵) and Satan (sadan mogui 撒旦魔鬼) are also present (McLeister 2019, 136). The latter have the ability to possess, harm, and "play tricks" (kaiwanxiao 开玩笑) on mortal humans such as hiding their glasses (McLeister 2019, 130-131; 136). Consequently, humans must be careful to avoid sinful acts as sin creates a break or opening (pokou 破口) through which evil spirits can influence and even dominate one's life (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God and that which belongs to god (such as Jesus and the Holy Spirit) are morally and hierarchically superior to Satan and evil spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Although god is omnipotent, Satan and evil spirits are not and so their powers may be considered domain-specific (having to do with sin and evil acts).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: God is omniscient and so aware at all times of everything that everyone does. As well, evil spirits (xieling 邪灵) are aware of humans and can influence or dominate a person's life if that person commits a sin that creates a break or opening through which the evil spirit can enter (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: For example, Christians generally avoid the characters for snake and dragon when choosing names for their children due to association with snakes and the serpent in the Genesis narrative and the dragons in the Book of Revelations.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Most Christians would abstain from drinking blood and food offered to household gods and other deities because it is believed that doing so would open the Christian up to attack from evil spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that spaces sacred to other religions such as temples and mosques are under the influence of evil spirits. Therefore, to enter them is to put Christians at risk of exposure to evil influences on their lives.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that objects sacred to other religions such as divining devices or prayer wheels are under the influence of evil spirits. Therefore, to use them is to put Christians at risk of exposure to evil influences on their lives.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Christians should abstain from sexual promiscuity or prostitution, for example, to avoid coming under the influence of evil spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: It isn't high on the agenda of church leaders but there is a connection made between cleanliness and righteous living and between dirt/unhygienic behaviours and evil spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Sin

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Those who are wicked are punished in Hell when they die. As well, because God is all powerful and benevolent, the acts of evil spirits and Satan may be interpreted as acts of punishment conducted, ultimately, in line with God's will. However, it is not always clear that believers themselves offer this interpretation or if they perceive evil spirits as obstacles to be combated (McLeister 2019, 136).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings such as Satan or evil spirits could be agents of divine punishment/judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Could be done via circumstances.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Those who are good are reward in Heaven when they die. As well, prayers can be conducted to

gain support for church members on a variety of personal issues such as one's health or encouraging one's child to marry (McLeister 2019, 130). However, it is unclear if the latter are considered "rewards" in a strict sense.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common

people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: As with other branches of Christianity, Protestantism's central tenet is that Jesus Christ is the messiah and that he will return at the end of the world as a saviour to create the kingdom of Heaven on earth. In doing so, Christ will "renew the Earth and reign over a new social order" (McLeister 2018, 10).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The purpose of the messiah is to save the souls of the faithful and to establish the kingdom of Heaven on earth. For more details, see the notes on "Eschatology" below.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: This question is answered "yes" only insofar as the kingdom of Heaven on earth will feature no distinction between "politics" and "religion."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: This question is answered "yes" only insofar as the kingdom of Heaven on earth will feature no distinction between "politics" and "religion."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: As noted above, the purpose of the messiah is to save the faithful.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Although not an overt aspect of TSPM-affiliated churches, eschatological and messianic beliefs can be thought of as, to use Malcolm Hamilton's term, constituting an "body of underground ideas and thought which circulates in a community" (McLeister 2018, 8). The eschaton is referred to as the Last Days (zuihoude rizi 最后的日子 or mori 末日) and is thought to be presaged by the world becoming increasingly chaotic, as well as other signs such as environmental degradation and the Chinese government's support of other religions as a counter to Protestantism. In addition to marking the end of the world, the eschaton is thought to result in a "New Heaven and a New Earth" (xintian xindi 新天新地) (McLeister 2018, 5). Between 2014-2016, a campaign in Zhejiang referred to as the Three Rectifications, One Demolition Campaign" (Sangai yichai xingdong 三改一拆行动) resulted in some church demolitions and forcible removal of crosses. Although the TSPM-affiliated churches in Huanghaicheng were in a different province, this Campaign raised anxieties among church members that this might mark the beginning of a wider persecution of Christianity in China. This anxiety catalyzed the underground body of eschatological and messianic beliefs as such a persecution was thought to be a sign of the last days (McLeister 2018, 5).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: While this may be generally true, the "Three Rectifications, One Demolition Campaign" (Sangai yichai xingdong 三改一拆行动) in Zhejiang escalated fears among the members of TSPM-affiliated churches in Huanghaicheng that the "Last days" (zuihoude rizi 最后的日子 or mori 末日) might be imminent (McLeister 2018).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to marking the end of the world, the eschaton is thought to result in a "New Heaven and a New Earth" (xintian xindi 新天新地) (McLeister 2018, 5).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: This question is answered "yes" only insofar as the kingdom of Heaven on earth will feature no distinction between "politics" and "religion."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: This question is answered "yes" only insofar as the kingdom of Heaven on earth will feature no distinction between "politics" and "religion."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: In order to be saved one must be a member of the faithful. Thus, one must take care not to "fall away" from the true faith of Protestantism in order to survive the eschaton (McLeister 2018, 10).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: Faith

Notes: Among the members of TSPM-affiliated churches in Huanghaicheng during the Zhejiang campaign, there was much concern that many might be weak and "fall away" from the church as a result of the persecutions of Christians that were thought to mark the eschaton. Consequently, only those whose faith was strong until the end would be saved (McLeister 2018, 16).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Because true morality is based on God's commands, this moral code is thought to take precedence in instances where it clashes with conventional morality. That being said, members of TSPM-affiliated churches and church leaders still attempted to follow conventional norms and societal

laws (McLeister 2021).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: True morality comes from God and is articulated in the precepts that he ordains.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Courage (generic):**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Generosity / charity:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Selflessness / selfless giving:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ **Righteousness / moral rectitude:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at Sunday worship is a mandatory aspect of being part of a TSPM-affiliated church congregation. There are also a variety of other church activities that congregations are encouraged to participate in including Bible study, proselytizing efforts, and prayer meetings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Because God is the source of true morality, becoming a member of a TSPM-affiliated church necessarily means accepting the ethical precepts that God has ordained.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is a common private (and public) ritual performed by all members of TSPM-affiliated churches. Although household or "house-churches" do exist, these are typically unregistered and so not officially part of the TSPM (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Weekly worship on Sundays is required for members of TSPM-affiliated churches. These meetings include hymns, Bible readings, and sermons. Although they vary in size, they may be considered "large-scale" as they can involve over 1,100 people (McLeister 2019, 129).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: All lay members of the church are referred to as "brother" and "sister" (McLeister 2019, 130).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: However, church members may be involved in charitable work either inside or outside China (McLeister 2021, 257).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: However, church members may be involved in charitable work either inside or outside China (McLeister 2021, 257).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Although not an "institutionalized" form of care, pastoral work at TSPM-affiliated churches can include visiting the elderly as well as the sick and infirm. This work is carried about by religious professionals as well as senior lay members of church congregations (McLeister 2019, 130).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to providing seminaries for the training of pastors, the TSPM also provides Sunday School, Bible study classes, evangelism training, and foreign language study through its churches. In certain instances, other educational programs, such as parenting classes, may also be present (McLeister 2013, 239).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, the TSPM is, along with the National Christian Council (which handles pastoral and doctrinal issues) one of the "Two Committees" (lianghui 两会) that are responsible for administering Protestant churches in China. These committees have layered bureaucratic structures and are present at the national, provincial, municipal, and district levels (McLeister 2019, 128).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Because TSPM-affiliated churches are registered with the state through the Three Self Patriotic Movement, they necessarily interact with state bureaucratic organizations such as the Religious Affairs Bureau (zongjiaoju 宗教局). As well, church members interact with the same state organs as any other citizen, such as Urban Management (chengguan 城管). In certain instances, church leaders may also need to interact with the Public Security Bureau (gong'anju 公安局) in instances where church members are perceived to violate state regulations (McLeister 2013, 241). For full discussions of church interactions with the state, see McLeister 2013 and McLeister 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: It's against the law for members of the military to be a member of a religious organization. In theory, there could be members of the military who attend Three-Self-affiliated churches but they would do so in a clandestine manner.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: TSPM-affiliated churches adhere to the Christian ritual calendar, which focuses on major festivals such as Easter and Christmas. As well, many TSPM-affiliated churches maintain active calendars of church events such as Bible studies, prayer meetings, youth meetings, Sunday worship, Sunday school, programs for teenagers to study the Bible, foreign languages, and evangelism, and parenting classes (McLeister 2013, 239).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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